

USER-CENTRED CIVIL INFRASTRUCTURE RELIABLE ASSESSMENT AND HEALING

Transforming how Europe
inspects, maintains and repairs
its critical civil infrastructure.

The SARAH project officially launched on 01-06-2025 to transform how Europe inspects, maintains and repairs its critical civil infrastructure.

Its human-centred, safe-by-design integrated digital platform embracing, sensors, digital twins, metaverse technologies and augmented reality to support supervisors and field teams in planning, execution, and reporting - while boosting safety and skills.

Key innovations include:

- Advanced sensors for corrosion, soil anchors, and crack monitoring
- Lightweight drones for rapid sensor deployment or interrogation and repairs
- A real-time digital twin with a decision engine ranking repair needs with 98% accuracy
- Remote expert assistance and AR guidance, achieving 80% user satisfaction
- Automated, AI-driven certification reports in standardized formats

Coordinated by CEA-Leti, SARAH unites leading European industries, universities, and research centres to deliver a scalable, interoperable solution that extends the life of viaducts, slopes, and ropeways - cutting costs and environmental impact while embracing Industry 5.0 principles.

Learn more about SARAH, our progress, the impact we're aiming towards and connect with us;
We're looking forward!

Inside:

- **Human-Centred Design:**
An introduction and the application in SARAH
- **Use Cases:**
From ropeways to slopes and viaducts - SARAH solutions applied
- **Coming up:**
What's up next on the SARAH agenda and how to stay connected.

HUMAN-CENTRED DESIGN

Human-Centred Design Approach

The SARAH project focuses on a human-centred design approach to develop safe, sustainable, and resilient technology. By integrating human factors thinking, knowledge, and methods, SARAH aims to understand current work practices and contexts, and address the needs of system designers and workers. The project enhances designers' human factors knowledge, facilitating solutions that incorporate these considerations into dialogues between designers and end-users.

Understanding individual features, work characteristics, group dynamics and organizational performance helps designers to identify user needs at all levels and develop human-centric services and equipment. Human factors benefit system designers, experts, and workers throughout technology development, ensuring usability, ergonomics, and safety. SARAH promises an engaging journey through collaboration with partners. Human factors—it's us! Let's realize those together.

"We are excited to explore and promote a human-centric approach to the digital maintenance of civil infrastructure. User-centred, safe, and sustainable digital systems, will benefit us all in the future."

ANNA-MARIA TEPERI, FIOH
HUMAN FACTORS

80%

Satisfaction at intervention workers, evaluated via interviews

15%

Reduction of high-risk work tasks

100%

Participation to the HF orientation within the consortium

Use Case Scenario 1. Ropeway

This use case focuses on monitoring and maintaining a structural element of a ropeway constructed in a marine environment.

It aims to ensure infrastructure integrity by tracking corrosion and crack propagation using sensors, enabling predictive maintenance and early failure anticipation. These measurements will feed a digital twin to identify critical maintenance zones and prioritize timely interventions. Data will be accessible via the metaverse, and inspection reports will be generated with generative AI.

Use Case Scenario 2. Slopes

This use case aims to monitor slope stability by tracking the performance of anchors throughout the construction of a high-speed rail line.

With the implementation of this use-case new sensors for load monitoring will verify the integrity of the anchors and collect data on the load they support—technically referred to as grout or adhesion forces. The collected data will be transmitted to the metaverse platform and used in autonomous UAS inspections to evaluate the correct installation and functioning of the sensors.

Use Case Scenario 3. Viaducts

Use case 3 demonstrates the application of autonomous UAS technologies for the inspection, maintenance, repair and monitoring of a viaduct.

Autonomous UAS will be used for unattended visual inspections, enabling continuous structural assessment without human intervention. Additionally, UAS will support sensor deployment and data collection, ensuring efficient monitoring of key structural parameters. Crack repair capabilities using UAS will be validated in controlled environments. These innovations aim to enhance maintenance efficiency, reduce manual inspection needs, and support scalable deployment across similar infrastructure.

Let's connect: we are looking forward to your visit and connection on our LinkedIn channel.
Visit our website for details.

SARAH Kick-Off Meeting Participants

Project Phase 1 recap

As we conclude this first edition of the SARAH Newsletter, it resembles a first but important step in our project. With the successful starting phase being completed, we also achieved our first milestone and are now looking forward to the next activities in the project.

ISABELLE DOR, CEA
COORDINATOR
ADMIN

"During its first months, SARAH's project has enthusiastically & successfully brought together leading European technical actors, SSH & safety engineering experts and critical infrastructure operators to define the system architecture integrating SSH insights in the design of SARAH digital solution."

NICOLAS GARRAUD, CEA
COORDINATOR TECH

"The SARAH project began with fruitful exchanges among participants from diverse backgrounds, defining the system architectures to be developed with the strategic objective to strengthen the safety of Europe's critical infrastructures."

Coming up in the SARAH project

While continuing the work on human-factor integration and technical development, in the coming phase of the project, we will also focus on strengthening strategic guidance, expanding our network, and increasing the visibility and impact of our work.

An international advisory board will be established to provide expert insight, ensure scientific and practical relevance, and support long-term positioning. In parallel, we will intensify ecosystem building by fostering collaborations across disciplines, sectors, and regions, creating a strong and engaged community around the project.

Targeted dissemination activities will translate results into accessible formats for diverse audiences, while a series of high-quality publications will share key findings with the broader scientific and professional community.

WHAT TO EXPLORE IN NEWSLETTER #2:

Technical Solutions:

An in-depth look at our technical solutions: what they are, how they work, and why they matter

Voices from the consortium:

Personal insights and reflections from the partners driving the project forward

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101178082. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.